

The role of the *Drosophila* scarface gene in feeding behaviour

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

The project will create non-human (*Drosophila melanogaster*) data exclusively. Each assay will be performed on four genotypes: CantonS (wild-type), scarface mutants (scaf27), overexpression, and knock-down flies. Each assay will be performed in quadruplicate on a minimum of 20 flies per replicate.

The data will consist of:

- **Volumes of food consumed**
 - **Capillary feeder (CAFE) assay:** The volume of food ingested will be recorded by measuring the food remaining in a glass capillary after varying feeding times (3h - 24h) using digital callipers and noting down in lab books. The data will be digitised and stored as comma-separated values (CSV) and will include genotype, food type, replicate number and volume of food consumed.
 - **Dye ingestion assay:** The volume of dye-labelled food ingested will be recorded by measuring the dye concentration in homogenised flies using a spectrophotometer. Spectrophotometer readings will be saved as CSV and annotated with genotype, food type and replicate number. Food volumes will be calculated from the absorbance values using a standard curve.
- **Outcomes of binary food choice assays:** will be collected as CSV and consist of genotype, food choice 1, food choice 2, replicate number, number of flies on each food and preference index. The total size of the data will not exceed 100MB

II. Standards and metadata

The data will be accompanied with rich metadata. Where possible, this metadata will be organised using existing ontologies, complemented with additional free text descriptions of the data. Biological metadata (organism, strain, developmental stage, sex, tissue and genotype) will be stored in Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) (format ebi.ac.uk/efo/). Diet composition will be stored in Compositional Dietary Nutrition Ontology (CDNO) format (ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/cdno). Fly genotypes will be stored in Flybase stock ontology (wiki.flybase.org/wiki/FlyBase:Controlled_vocabularies_used_by_FlyBase).

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

The study will generate original primary data

IV. Secondary use

Researchers studying molecular determinants of feeding behaviour could benefit from this data.

V. Methods for data sharing

Raw data and associated metadata will be published as supplemental data to a research paper describing the results, or through publication of a dedicated data publication, for example, in Zenodo (zenodo.org/). In the latter case, the Digital Object Identifier pointing to the data publication will be included in all subsequent papers that make use of this data.

VI. Proprietary data

No human, sensitive, proprietary or patentable data will be produced or used in this study. We do not foresee any restrictions or delays in data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

All data will be made available upon publication or within three years of generation of the dataset, whichever comes first. As no human, sensitive, proprietary or patentable data will be produced or used in this study, we do not foresee any restrictions or delays in data sharing.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

All data will be stored as CSV.